

Photochemical Reduction of Tungstic and Molybdic Acids.

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Several years ago, Wassiljewa (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1913, 12, 1) observed that freshly prepared sol of tungstic acid could be reduced to the blue coloured lower oxide by reducing agents like ethyl alcohol, glucose, formaldehyde, etc., when exposed to sunlight. He found that the photochemical activity of tungstic acid sol towards reduction decreases as the sol is allowed to age and it can be regained by heating the sol to a higher temperature. Freundlich (*"Kapillar, Chemie"* 1922, p. 872) attributes this behaviour of tungstic acid sol to the difference in the degree of hydration of the colloidal particles with the age of the sol. In previous papers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 1905; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 184, 135) we have investigated the ageing of the sols of tungstic and molybdic acids and have concluded that these sols when freshly prepared contain a large proportion of these substances in the molecular condition (simple or aggregated) and the following equilibrium exists in the sol:

We have shown that when the sols of molybdic and tungstic acids are kept at the room temperature, more and more of aggregated molecules and colloidal particles are formed at the expense of simple molecules. We have remarked in the above communications that the decrease in the photochemical activity of tungstic acid sol with time can be more fully explained by assuming that most of the tungstic acid present in the molecular condition polymerises into larger molecules or to colloidal particles, which are not chemically active as the simple molecules.

In this paper we have investigated the photochemical reduction of molybdic acid sol, freshly prepared and aged into the lower oxide, with a view to examine if similar behaviour is developed in the

case of molybdic acid, as observed by Wassiljewa with tungstic acid sol. We have already shown that the different monovalent cations exert a coagulating effect on the sols of molybdic and tungstic acids and are in the following decreasing order $\text{Rb}^+ > \text{NH}_4^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$.

Accordingly we have carried out some experiments on the photochemical reduction of tungstic and molybdic acid sols in the presence of these monovalent cations in amounts insufficient to cause complete coagulation.

Sols of tungstic and molybdic acids were prepared by adding equivalent amounts of hydrochloric acid to solutions of sodium tungstate and ammonium molybdate, ethyl alcohol being used as the reducing agent.

The reacting mixtures with different electrolytes were contained in test tubes, kept in a thermostat, the temperature of which was maintained within ± 0.1 and exposed to sunlight.

The development of colour was followed by a Nutting's spectrophotometer. To isolate any particular region of the spectrum for ease of comparison, a shutter red eye-piece was employed. The source of light was a 100 c.p. point-o-lite lamp working at 220 volts. Two similar neutral-tint glass cells with optically plane parallel ends were used—one for the solution whose extinction coefficient had to be observed and the other for an equal volume of distilled water so that the comparison might be made under identical conditions of original light intensity.

The time taken in the actual reading of the scale after the comparison of the two spectra did not exceed 45 seconds and precautions were taken to ensure constancy of temperature during this interval. To obtain the extinction coefficient, the Bunsen-Roscoe formula was employed and readings were taken on the "Density-Scale" of the rotating circle. Thus the extinction coefficient is given by $\Sigma = \frac{D}{t}$ where "D" is the reading on the density scale and equal to $2 \log_{10} \tan \theta$, " θ " being the angular reading and t the thickness in centimeters of the absorbing substance.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1. Molybdic acid was prepared by adding equivalent amount of HCl to 2% ammonium molybdate solution.

TABLE I.
15 C.c. molybdic acid sol + 0.8 c.c. absolute alcohol.
Temperature = 26.5°.

Condition.	Time in min.	Extinction coefficient.	k_e Zero-molecular.
Fresh sample	12	0.56	—
	24	0.90	0.0284
	36	1.26	0.0290
	48	1.65	0.0300
			Mean 0.0291
Old sample	8	0.44	—
	20	0.76	0.0287
	32	1.06	0.0258
	44	1.36	0.0255
			Mean 0.0260
Old sample heated to 70° for 8 minutes.	4	0.20	—
	16	0.62	0.036
	28	1.04	0.035
	40	1.46	0.035
			Mean 0.035

TABLE II.
10 C.c. molybdic acid + 3 c.c. water + 2 c.c. water or electrolyte + 0.3 c.c. absolute alcohol.

Condition.	Time in min.	Extinction coefficient.	k_e Zero-molecular.
2 c.c. water	5	0.02	—
	20	0.32	0.020
	35	0.61	0.0196
	50	0.92	0.020
			Mean 0.0199
2 c.c. N/10-NaCl	10	0.08	—
	25	0.34	0.0173
	40	0.58	0.0187
	55	0.81	0.0163
			Mean 0.0166
2 c.c. N/10-KCl	5	0.05	—
	15	0.16	0.0120
	24	0.26	0.0117
	33	0.35	0.0112
			Mean 0.0116
2 c.c. N/10-RbCl	15	0.28	—
	30	0.38	0.0087
	45	0.50	0.0073
	60	0.59	0.0069
			Mean 0.00697
2 c.c. N/10-LiCl	9	0.12	—
	18	0.29	0.0190
	27	0.45	0.0180
	36	0.60	0.0177
			Mean 0.0182

2. Tungstic acid was prepared by adding equivalent amount of HCl to *M*/10-sodium tungstate solution.

TABLE III.

10 C.c. tungstic acid + 0.5 c.c. alcohol + 4.5 c.c. water or electrolyte.

Temperature = 15 c.c.		Total volume = 25°.	
Condition.	Time in min.	Extinction coefficient	k_0 Zero molecular.
4.5 c.c. water.	3	0.08	—
	15	0.20	0.0117
	27	0.34	0.0118
	39	0.48	0.0118
			Mean 0.0118
2 <i>N</i> -LiCl	6	0.12	—
	18	0.24	0.0100
	30	0.38	0.0100
	42	0.47	0.0097
			Mean 0.0099
2 <i>N</i> -NaCl	9	0.14	—
	21	0.25	0.0091
	33	0.35	0.0087
	45	0.46	0.0089
			Mean 0.0089
2 <i>N</i> -KCl	12	0.17	—
	24	0.28	0.0075
	36	0.36	0.0079
	48	0.45	0.0077
			Mean 0.0077

The photochemical reduction of the sols of molybdic and tungstic acids by ethyl alcohol thus follows the zero-molecular law. On the other hand, Wassiljewa found that the reduction follows the mono-molecular law. Reduction cannot be observed in the dark. Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1856) has shown that the order of a photochemical reaction is generally decreased in the presence of light and this decrease is most remarkable in the chemical reactions which are highly photosensitive such as the present ones.

It may be interesting to note that the velocity constant of freshly prepared molybdic acid sol decreases from 0.0291 to 0.0260 when it is allowed to age for two days. When, however, the sol is heated to 70° for about 8 minutes the velocity constant is increased

to 0.085 and it is greater than the velocity constant of the freshly prepared sol. We have already shown in a separate paper (*loc. cit.*) that molybdic acid gradually polymerises to bigger molecules on ageing and when the sol is heated, the aggregated molecules again broken up into simple molecules.

The sols become less photochemically active in the presence of monovalent cations, and the velocity constants are smaller than that of the fresh sol. The order in which the cations affect the velocity constants are in the order $\text{Rb} > \text{K} > \text{Na} > \text{Li}$, Rb decreasing the velocity constant to the greatest extent and Li the least.

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Received May 12, 1930.

